

RI-VIS D5.2 Online Communication Platform and Toolkit

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
<i>Detailed report on the deliverable</i>	2
Background/Introduction	2
Description of work	3
Adaptation of toolkit to online format.....	3
Enhancements to ARIA SiteBuilder for toolkit implementation	4
Conclusion/Next steps	7

Executive Summary

To become sustainable over time, European research infrastructures must increase their visibility, both individually and collectively. This requires the harmonization of the strategies, tools, guidelines and resources that European research infrastructures use in their communication. To achieve this goal, the RI-VIS project developed the “Communication Toolkit for European Research Infrastructures”, which stemmed from the collective effort of 31 communication experts representing 17 European research infrastructures that gathered during three workshops. In turn, this collective effort gave way to the informal establishment of a network of professionals working in European RI communication, with visible outputs regarding the exchange of best-practices and problem solving in their field of work. This task developed an online platform to improve the usability of the Communication Toolkit by RI communications and enable the sharing of information and resources withing the RI communication experts’ network. The online platform was developed on ARIA and it is hosted in <https://toolkit.ri-vis.eu/>. It presents 4 main sections:

- **About** – with information on how to use the platform and how to engage with the comms network.
- **Style guide** – including a common glossary, jargon buster, key messages, analogy and storytelling tools.
- **Guidelines** - including guidelines and tips to develop RI webpages, social media strategies and targeted communication approaches to RI counterparts outside of Europe, the private sector, and decision-makers.
- **Resources** - including available communication materials developed for European RIs.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

Internationalization is a key ingredient for the long-term sustainability of research infrastructures. Improving cooperation with strategic partners and stakeholders is a main measure to tackle the challenges posed by the need to better structure the international dimension of research infrastructures. Hence, to become sustainable over time, European research infrastructures must increase their visibility, both individually and collectively.

To increase the visibility of European infrastructures – to multiple stakeholders in Europe and beyond - their communication must become more effective and consistent. This requires the harmonization of the strategies, tools, guidelines and resources that European research infrastructures use in their communication, thus contributing to consolidate the very concept of “research infrastructures” and improve how different stakeholders perceive them. European research infrastructures must start “speaking the same language” and effectively engage with different sectors, thus increasing their collective visibility and consolidating their presence in the scientific research realm.

Description of work

Adaptation of toolkit to online format

Task 5.1 gathered 31 communication experts from 17 research infrastructures over three workshops to develop a manual of best practice and materials with a common language and standards. The outputs of these workshops were two-folded:

1. They enabled the development of the “Communication Toolkit for European Research Infrastructures” (deliverable D5.1) – a PDF document that included common standards, guidelines and resources tailored to the existing capacities and to the needs and constraints of communicating European research infrastructures to specific stakeholder-groups in Europe and beyond.
2. They also promoted the informal establishment of a network of professionals working in European RI communication, with visible advantages regarding the exchange of best-practices and problem solving in their field of work.

To ensure the sustainability of this toolkit after the end of RI-VIS, along with its widespread use by more European research infrastructures, we transposed it into an online format. An online presence adds visibility to the toolkit and ensures that it is more user-friendly. This work was done in articulation with RI-VIS WP4 in view of hosting the Toolkit’s website on the ARIA platform (D4.1).

All the contents developed for the Communication Toolkit were included in the online platform, however they were adapted to web. The structure of the toolkit structure was also redefined for an easier navigation through menus/submenus and to enable the sharing of additional relevant resources that are useful for RI communication professionals. The online platform is hosted in <https://toolkit.ri-vis.eu/> and it presents 4 main sections:

- **About**
This menu presents instructions for users on how to use the platform and how to engage with the comms professionals’ network on Slack. It also provides a brief overview on how the Communication Toolkit was developed, referring to the RI-VIS project.
- **Style guide**
Several submenus within this menu focus on communication features that are common to all RIs, providing tips and resources that will help harmonize and simplify their communication. These include:
 - A glossary that aims to harmonize how we describe research infrastructures and their terminology.

- A jargon buster with tips on how to cut through complexity and achieve a clear communication.
- A few key messages that are common to all research infrastructures and which can be incorporate into the communication of all European RIs.
- A very simple analogy to convey how research infrastructures work.
- A storytelling approach to convey why we need research infrastructures in Europe.
- **Guidelines**

This menu provides general guidelines and a few tips and tricks on:

 - Developing an RI website in which users can easily navigate and understand what RIs are.
 - Creating a social media strategy tailored to each RI, including some common hashtags that may be used by all European research infrastructures.
 - Developing specific targeted communication approaches to reach out to the RI counterparts outside of Europe, the private sector and decision-makers.
- **Resources**

This menu the possibility of sharing available communication materials and resources developed for European RIs or that may be useful for RI comms professionals (e.g.: manuals, white papers, multimedia and print materials, etc.).

In addition to these 4 main sections, a fifth section “Community” points to the RI Communications group on Slack that was promoted during the RI-VIS project. Gathering over 250 RI communication experts, this platform enables the sharing of ideas and experiences to improve the communication of European RIs.

Enhancements to ARIA SiteBuilder for toolkit implementation

We had previously described the development of a new community content management system within the ARIA software suite under task 4.1. This system, ARIA SiteBuilder, was the basis for the online implementation of the toolkit. ARIA SiteBuilder was further developed with new block types for sub-menus and document sharing, improved menu and internal link management, block editing tools, and version control. Additionally, the latest version of ARIA SiteBuilder now supports configurable page visibility and editing permissions for users and groups.

Menu management

ARIA SiteBuilder was extended to support multiple independent menus. In its first iteration, ARIA SiteBuilder had one main navigation menu at the top which would convert to a “hamburger menu” which opens in a drawer for mobile devices. The footer, a global block at the bottom of each page, was also developed with menu support. A menu could be added to the footer with links.

To manage the menus, configuration options open in a drawer to the left when the manage menu button is clicked. The menu to be edited is selected from a dropdown list of all site

Figure 1: Menu editor drawer for configuration of independent menus

menus at the top. Global settings for the menu such as its name can be edited by clicking the pencil icon when that menu is selected and brand new menus can be created by clicking the plus.

The menu editor is displayed in Figure 1 for the menu “Social Media Strategy”. There are three types of menu item which can be added: “Pages” for linking to internal pages within the site, Link “for linking to any other URL”, and “Folder” which does not direct anywhere but can be used to organise groups of pages or links.

Order of menu items and any nesting of items can be changed by dragging and dropping and the settings of individual menu items e.g. titles can be changed by clicking the ellipsis beside the item to be changed.

Menus created here can be applied to the header, footer and to sub-menu blocks.

New block types

Menu block: A use-case defined by the toolkit team was to enable easy navigation through pages which may be deeply nested within sub-menus e.g. for navigation within subsections of the toolkit. This was developed as an accordion menu block which could be added to any page and can display as default expanded or default closed. An example menu block for the “Social Media Strategy” menu is shown in Figure 2.

Document block: The purpose of the document block is to present documents on pages for inspection and download. Page editors can select one or more documents to display in the document block from a list of documents uploaded in the ARIA network associated with the site (see webinar “Using ARIA for RI-VIS: Networks, forums, content and more” for more information about ARIA networks). The selected documents will then display in a grid with their title and buttons to download the file or view more details in a pop-out window.

Figure 2: Sub-menu block displaying expanded view of Social Media Strategy menu

Figure 3: Document block with "details" window expanded

Page permissions and version control

Version management: When editing a page, the user is prompted to either edit the live page, in which case any changes are automatically applied, or to create a new version of the page which allows the page content to be modified without any changes to what is displayed outside of edit mode. This allows for editors to work on a page and review it before publishing, and also allows older versions of a page to be preserved when content changes if desired. Editors can navigate between versions of any page using the version dropdown in the editor bar at the top. The version which is currently live can be selected from all available versions of the page.

Figure 4: Page editor navigation, version, visibility and sharing options

In the case of the toolkit, this feature enables revisions of the content to be made and reviewed by the toolkit team before being made available to the wider community.

Public, private and offline pages: Page visibility for each page is one of three options: "Online" where the page is publicly available to anyone and you do not need to be logged in to view the content, "Private" where individual users or groups can be selected and only these people will be able to view the page content when they are logged in (Note that content viewers are not necessarily able to edit the page content as this is separately controlled), and "Offline" where the page is only visible to page editors when they are logged into the site.

Though the main toolkit pages are currently publicly shared, and public sharing of material is encouraged where possible, there are cases where material to be shared is not for wide distribution. By having "Private" pages the toolkit will allow more restricted sharing, for example of useful draft documents, within a gated selection of users in the community which will be used as the toolkit expands.

Sharing links and page editors: Page editors (which are distinct from "viewers" of private pages) can be added to individual pages or on a site-wide level. These individuals will be able to make changes to block content on a page including adding and removing blocks. There are occasions where it may be necessary to share content with non-page editors for their

Figure 5: External sharing link for pages

feedback before publishing it. To make this possible any page can be shared by generating a unique link which will display the page irrespective of its visibility level.

New block editing tools

Cloning: This allows an existing block to be duplicated in a new block on the same page.

Relative link to block: This copies to the system clipboard an anchor link to that block on the page. This link can be used anywhere to link directly to that block.

Figure 6: Block editing options including relative links and block cloning

Conclusion/Next steps

The development of the Communication Toolkit for Research Infrastructures enabled the development of a network of professionals that work in the communication of research infrastructures all over Europe. To be able to share views, experiences, constraints and advances to peers is key to improve the success of our work, hence the practitioners that form this community have demonstrated interest in continuing working together and supporting each other.

This deliverable aims to support this community of communication experts, along with a dedicated Slack channel and other activities that bring together these experts, such as the online social media and marketing training activities defined as Milestone 9 of task 5.1 (M 30, New Skills for Communication Officers).

To ensure the update of the online toolkit, the kit will be disseminated to communication officers through our communication expert community. The toolkit will also be promoted through social media and through outreach activities of the RI-VIS project and partner infrastructures.

For future development of the toolkit, the resources section will be expanded with more examples and material from the growing communication community established by task 5.1. Versioning features and simple editing tools within the ARIA SiteBuilder platform enables changes and updates to be made to toolkit content quickly and easily by those with permission to do so. The ERIC Forum has agreed to support this toolkit after the conclusion of the RI-VIS project providing sustainability for the materials and ensuring they are kept up-to-date.